

SATELLITE COMMUNICATIONS FOR FIGHTERS

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ABSTRACT With the demise of the Soviet Union, the threat to the United States and its allies has changed. Instead of a single advisory and a defined theater of battle, U.S. forces face worldwide deployment in support of Peace Keeping activities and regional conflicts. In the new world order, U.S. Forces will require flexible, worldwide, jam-resistant, low-probability-of-intercept communications, including space-premium fighters. The Integrated CNI Subsystem (ICNIS), which includes Milstar satellite communications, could satisfy that need by upgrading the integrated avionics suite of existing fighters. Many of the Milstar functions, such as frequency conversion, signal processing, detection, display, and control could be performed in the ICNIS common avionics modules. The Milstar antenna for the fighter would be a hybrid, solid-state phased array being developed by Rome Laboratory for the Milstar frequency band--20 GHz receive and 44 GHz transmit. A feasibility study for the Integrated CNI Subsystem is currently underway. A brassboard development, demonstration, and flight test is also underway for the Integrated Tactical Milstar to demonstrate the Milstar satellite communications functions as part of a common avionics suite.

INTRODUCTION

With the new world order, the need for more flexible basing of military forces has become apparent. The lack of extensive foreign basing of U.S. forces and the prospect of Peace Keeping or regional conflicts anywhere in the world requires a worldwide, jam-resistant, low-probability-of-intercept communications system to support our fighter aircraft. Tying a fighter to a line-of-sight radio link with an E-3 AWACS or E-8 J-STARS will not provide the flexibility required in the future. One answer is a satellite communications (SATCOM) link that is distant independent.

For the past 20 years, the Avionics Directorate of the Wright Laboratory (WL) has been pursuing an integrated avionics concept for Air Force aircraft to combine communications, navigation, and identification functions in an integrated suite of hardware/firmware/software. The integrated avionics approach offers the advantages of increased reliability with shared resources, smaller size, and the ability to reprogram resources to add new or modified function with minimum change to

the aircraft installation, Borky, 1992. WL's Integrated Communication, Navigation, Identification Avionics (ICNIA) program has recently successfully delivered Advanced Development Models (ADMs) of the ICNIA hardware and several new aircraft programs have benefited from the transition of this technology. While ICNIA was designed as a total avionics system for new aircraft, a new initiative Integrated CNI Subsystem (ICNIS) is planned to retrofit into existing first-line fighter aircraft, Keen, 1992. The ICNIS would provide a number of high-payoff avionics functions such as GPS, IFF, Microwave Landing System (MLS), TACAN, and Milstar SATCOM.

THE PROBLEM

ADDING ANYTHING TO A FIGHTER

The ability to package the ICNIA functions such as GPS, IFF, MLS, and TACAN in a software intensive common avionics system is being demonstrated with the F-22 Common Avionics program. The same is not true with the Milstar system being developed by the Space & Missile Center of Los Angeles AFB CA which is designed to provide secure, survivable, jam-resistant low-probability-of-intercept communications for the Strategic and Tactical forces, Schultz, 1983. The original Milstar concept was to concentrate on communications for the nuclear capable forces. With the recent changes in world politics, Congress directed that the Milstar system be redefined to put more emphasis on supporting tactical communications, Figure 1.

The current airborne Milstar terminals being developed by the Electronics Systems Center of Hanscom AFB MA are designed for use on airborne command post aircraft. A smaller version, the Low Cost Terminal (LCT), is also being developed for aircraft requiring a smaller, less capable terminal. The original airborne force-element version of Milstar terminal consists of multiple electronics boxes and mounting trays in addition to a steerable dish antenna. The total weight of the system is approximately 600 pounds, including cabling, mounting hardware, and radome. The LCT version will significantly reduce the volume to a few boxes plus the antenna, with a total weight of approximately 230 pounds. While the LCT is less than one-eighth the size and one-third the weight of the original force element terminal version, it is still too large to fit in space-

Figure 1. Changing Role of Satellite Communications

premium fighter aircraft. Every pound and cubic inch of avionics added to the space-premium aircraft reduces its payload and range of operation. The problem is to find a way to add the Milstar function while not increasing the fighter's weight and volume more than a few pounds and a few cubic inches.

COMMON AVIONICS

The ICNIA program was a \$130 million advanced development program that has been underway in WL for the past 9 years. ICNIA was designed to integrate the functions of a number of stand-alone avionics systems using common (modular) allocatable resources. These resources include multi-band receivers, common signal/data processors, and multiple high-speed buses. The concept was to replace 15 to 20 stand-alone avionics systems with a few integrated, reprogrammable boxes, Figure 2.

The ICNIA ADMs were developed by TRW and delivered to WL for evaluation. A pictorial representation of the resources and functions in ICNIA is shown in Figure 3. By selecting functions from the right hand side of the Figure, resources on the left are allocated. Multiple functions can be supported simultaneously, such as UHF radio, VHF radio, TACAN, GPS,

IFF, and MLS. The operator can designate a priority for each function, so that in the event of the failure of a resource, the highest priority functions will be maintained at the expense of lower priority functions. This feature can dramatically improve the time between critical failures for the avionics system. Instead of providing spares for each stand-alone avionics function, there is a pool of spare modules that can be switched in to maintain critical avionics functions in the event of a failure or battle damage.

SOLUTION - INTEGRATED CNI SUBSYSTEM

The ICNIS is intended to provide a fault tolerant solution in a two Air Transport Rack (ATR) packages that would replace eight or ten existing stand-alone avionics boxes on existing fighter aircraft. The Ada software for most of the avionics functions can be transferred from the existing F-22 Common Avionics development. One function that is not being coded in the F-22 program is the Milstar. To provide the Milstar Ada code for the common avionics effort, WL has undertaken the Integrated Tactical Milstar (ITM) program. The concept of ITM is to reprogram some of the ICNIA resources to perform many of the standard Milstar functions, such as

Figure 2. ICNIA/AMICA Terminal Evolution

Figure 3. ICNIA Shared Resources Concept

frequency up-conversion/down-conversion, signal processing, detection, display, and control, Johnson & Foshee, 1992. Some of the Milstar functions are not currently performed in ICNIA at a high enough speed or accuracy. It will be necessary to add a new high-speed processor and a new frequency generation card to support Milstar, Figure 4. However, these new capabilities will not be dedicated to Milstar. For example, a higher-speed processor and more capable frequency generator will allow some existing avionics functions to be done better and allow easier expansion for future functions.

In a related effort, the Rome Laboratory (RL) is developing a hybrid, solid-state phased array antenna for the Milstar frequency band--20 GHz receive and 44 GHz transmit. These phased arrays will be able to electronically scan from the zenith down to 20 degrees above the horizon and thus point the antenna toward the Milstar satellite while in flight. Two different packaging approaches, based on a "brick" architecture to achieve closely spaced radiating elements, are currently being explored in a technology demonstration phase, Figures 5. In one array design, the basic building block is Monolithic Microwave Integrated Circuit (MMIC) phase shifters, amplifiers, and printed circuit dipole radiating elements mounted on 8-element cards or trays. In the second design, the radiating elements are individually loaded waveguides, each with an integrated MMIC phase shifter and amplifier module. In both designs, the active devices are mounted behind or perpendicular to the plane of the radiating elements.

Another challenge for the integrated concept is the cryptographic requirements of Milstar. In the airborne command post configuration, the Milstar cryptographic equipment occupies one complete five-foot-high equipment rack. To solve the space problem, an integrated crypto is under development at Motorola, Inc. The integrated crypto will handle 17 different cryptographic algorithms in a package size of 6" X 5" X 1". One integrated card will provide any two of the 17 cryptographic algorithms simultaneously. Since the Integrated Tactical Milstar will require only two of the 17 cryptos available, one integrated crypto card will satisfy the integrated Milstar terminal needs.

An initial Integrated Tactical Milstar Feasibility Study was completed in 1992. The study analyzed the Milstar functions and determined which ones could be performed in a modified ICNIA system. For the purpose of the study, tactical Milstar was defined as one, half-duplex Milstar 75 bit-per-second channel working through the Milstar satellite agile beam. The transmit and receive phased array antennas being developed by RL will provide the radio-frequency (RF) portion of the

system, including the antenna pointing electronics. The integrated avionics will interface with the antennas at an intermediate frequency and with control and frequency reference signals. The study concluded that a major portion of the Milstar functions could be accomplished in the ICNIA system by software/firmware reprogramming. The addition of the upgraded frequency synthesizer and high-speed processor would accomplish the remaining Milstar functions. With the successful completion of the ITM Study, the ITM development got underway in 1993. The development will include coding of the Milstar functions in Ada, modification of the ICNIA ADM software to support Milstar, and a flight testing demonstration of ITM in 1995/96.

CONCLUSIONS

The Integrated CNI Subsystem offers a lightweight, low volume solution to upgrading a federated avionics suite with a fault-tolerant avionics subsystem including the Milstar SATCOM. Following the ITM breadboard development, the ICNIS program has been defined to develop, flight test, and transition the Integrated Tactical Milstar to space-premium aircraft. Having Milstar on future high performance fighters offers a means of passing information on mobile threats and mobile targets via a secure, jam-resistant, low-probability-of-intercept communications system.

REFERENCES

- Borky, J.L., "Modular Integrated Avionics - Strategies and Challenges," *Journal of Electronic Defense*, Vol. 15 No. 5, May 1992.
- Johnson, A.L. & J.J Foshee, "Integrated Tactical Milstar For Fighters," MILCOM92, San Diego CA, 14 October 1992.
- Keen P.J., "Integrated Communications, Navigation, Identification Subsystem (ICNIS) For Existing Aircraft," MILCOM92, San Diego CA, 14 October 1992.
- Schultz, J.B., "Milstar to Close Dangerous C3I Gap," *Defense Electronics*, Vol. 15, No. 3, March 1983.

Figure 4. Conceptual Evolution of Integrated Tactical Milstar Terminal

Figure 5. Brick Packaging Concept For Milstar Phased-Array Antenna